

STUDY ON ROLE OF BANKING INSTITUTIONS IN RURAL DEVELOPMENT – AN EVALUATION

Mr. Rajesh Kumar

Asst Prof & Research Scholar,
Institute of Engineering & Technology Alwar (Raj.)

Dr. Bhupendra Kumar

Research Supervisor, Institute of Engineering & Technology Alwar (Raj.)

ABSTRACT

The government should encourage the banks to adopt financial inclusion by means of financial assistance, advertisement and awareness programs etc. to achieve the aim of 11th plan of Inclusive Growth. Rural people with low income often lack access to bank account and they have not time for multiple visits to avail the banking services, an effort is made by opening a savings bank account or availing a loan, these families find it more difficult to save and to plan financially for the future. This paper is an attempt to discuss the role of banking financial institutions for rural development in India. The real growth of Indian economy lies in the discharge of rural people from poverty, unemployment and socio-economic backwardness. Keeping this in a view, the Government of India implemented various programme for rural development. So, rural development means complete transformation of rural society from traditional way of living to modern way of living.

Key Words: Financial Inclusion, financial assistance, rural people, bank account, banking financial institutions, rural development, Programme, traditional and modern.

I. Introduction

In fact, access to affordable finance enables the poor and vulnerable groups to undertake economic activities and take advantage of growth opportunities for economic empowerment. Hence, developing an inclusive financial system to provide equal opportunities to all in accessing financial services at affordable costs is a pre-condition for achieving accelerated economic growth along with a reduction in income inequality and poverty. Without an inclusive financial system, poor and vulnerable section of the community and small and petty enterprises would not be in a position to take advantages of growth opportunities. And rural communities remain the largest unserved market for financial services. Traditionally, formal financial institutions have avoided or failed to offer sustainable services in rural areas (e.g. rural or agricultural development banks). Thus, informal or semi-formal financial institutions as well as alternative providers like traders or input suppliers have become major providers of financial services. However, these informal providers often have weak institutional and managerial capacity; and operating in isolation from the financial system has let some of these providers charge steep interest rates. People living in rural areas may need access to financial services to purchase agriculture inputs; obtain veterinary services; maintain infrastructure; contract labor for planting/harvesting; transport goods to markets; make/receive payments; manage peak season incomes to cover expenses in low seasons; invest in education, shelter, health; or deal with emergencies. Reserve Bank of India vision for 2020 is to open nearly 600 million new customers' accounts.

The primary Objectives of banking services in rural areas Poverty Alleviation Objective these objectives is to uplift the mass of population residing in the rural areas that are currently below the poverty line by extending credit to the smallest-scale economic activity and the secondary objective is financial intermediation objectives the approach involves increasing the accessibility of banking services to the poor in a commercially sustainable manner.

Need for Rural Banking

For a rapid expansion of rural banking in the country can be made out on the following grounds:

1. To correct imbalances
2. Provide Institutional Credit to Rural Areas
3. To mobilize rural savings
4. To integrate the money market
5. To induce Rapid Economic Development
6. **The Promotional Role:**

Review of Literature

Review of Literature done through following

1. Malhotra R.N., “Banking in 1990’s, PIGMY”, Economic Review, Monthly Economic Journal of Syndicate Bank, Vol. 35, No.7, February 1990, pp.1-3 and 8.
 - In his paper entitled “Banking Review,” he has analyzed that at present both RBI and NABARD are involved in various aspects of co-ordination and liaisoning at the district level. NABARD will be setting up offices in all the districts.
2. Karnati Lingaiah and C. Anjana Devi, “NABARD AND Rural Credit: A Profile”, Southern Economist, Vol.34, No.21, March 1, 1996, pp.23 and 24., “NABARD AND Rural Credit: A Profile”, Southern Economist.
 - In his paper entitled “NABARD AND Rural Credit ,” he has observes that the functions of NABARD, they indicate that NABARD provides short-term, medium term and long term and credit to State Cooperative Banks, Regional Rural Banks, Land Development Banks and other financial institutions approved by Reserve
3. Kishanjit Basu and Krishnan Jindal Micro-Finance Emerging Challenges Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company 2000, pp.1-5.
 - Microfinance as small scale financial services provided to the people who work in agriculture, fishing and herding. Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) who provide additional services also such as issue of cheques, drafts, guarantees, etc.
4. Shivamaggi, H.B., Reforms in Rural Banking: Need for a Holder Approach, Economic and Political Weekly, May 13, 2000

Leadership of NABARD and nongovernment organization (NGOs) is the formation of informal self help groups (SHGs) broadly on the model of the grameen banks of Bangladesh.

Objective of the Study

- To study the problems of rural areas and the scope of banking institutions in solving these problems.
- To study the role of Commercial Banks, Co-operative Banks in rural development, Regional Rural Banks in the rural development, National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development.
- To make a comparative study of the institutions engaged in the rural development and to assess the role of banking institutions in rural development.
- To identify the gaps and to suggest improvements in the existing system of rural banking.

Banking Institutions in Rural Development

The term rural banking refers to the functions of providing banking facilities and services to rural economic activities and does not limit itself to any one institution like a commercial bank, or a co-operative credit society or a regional rural bank. The banks play the significant role in the economic development of a country.

Their roles can be analysed under the following heads:

- 1) Financial Intermediation

- 2) Generation of Savings
- 3) Credit creation
- 4) Promotion of Liquidity
- 5) Inter-regional Mobilisation of Resources
- 6) Subsidiary Services

Commercial banking in India also developed originally in the cities and industrial centres in the country. Commercial banking, therefore, had an urban base. The objective of profit maximisation and the adherence to the real bills doctrine by the Indian commercial banks gave rise to certain imbalances in the Indian commercial banking system with their adverse repercussions on the balanced regional and sectoral development of the Indian economy.

These imbalances are;

- i) Regional imbalances
- ii) Local imbalances
- iii) Sectoral imbalances

Financial inclusion initiatives

- Advised all banks to open Basic Saving Bank Deposit (BSBD) accounts with minimum common facilities such as no minimum balance, deposit and withdrawal of cash at bank branch and ATMs, receipt/ credit of money through electronic payment channels, facility of providing ATM card.
- Relaxed and simplified KYC norms to facilitate easy opening of bank accounts, especially for small accounts with balances not exceeding Rs. 50,000 and aggregate credits in the accounts not exceeding Rs. one lakh a year. Further, banks are advised not to insist on introduction for opening bank accounts of customers. In addition, banks are allowed to use Aadhar Card as a proof of both identity and address.
- Simplified Branch Authorization Policy, to address the issue of uneven spread bank branches, domestic SCBs are permitted to freely open branches in Tier 2 to Tier 6 centers with population of less than 1 lakh under general permission, subject to reporting. In North-Eastern States and Sikkim domestic SCBs can open branches without having any permission from RBI. With the objective of further liberalizing, general permission to domestic scheduled commercial banks (other than RRBs) for opening branches in Tier 1 centers, subject to certain conditions.
- Compulsory Requirement of Opening Branches in Un-banked Villages, banks are directed to allocate at least 25% of the total number of branches to be opened during the year in un-banked (Tier 5 and Tier 6) rural centers.
- Opening of intermediate brick and mortar structure, for effective cash management, documentation, redressal of customer grievances and close supervision of BC operations, banks have been advised to open intermediate structures between the present base branch and BC locations. This branch could be in the form of a low cost simple brick and mortar structure consisting of minimum infrastructure such core banking solution terminal linked to a pass book printer and a safe for cash retention for operating larger customer transactions.
- Public and private sector banks had been advised to submit board approved three year Financial Inclusion Plan (FIP) starting from April 2010. These policies aim at keeping self-set targets in respect of rural brick and mortar branches opened, BCs employed, coverage of un-banked villages with population above 2000 and as well as below 2000, BSBD accounts opened, KCCs, GCCs issued and others. RBI has been monitoring these plans on a monthly basis.

- Banks have been advised that their FIPs should be disaggregated and percolated down up to the branch level. This would ensure the involvement of all stakeholders in the financial inclusion efforts.
- In June 2012, revised guidelines on Financial Literacy Centers (FLCs). Accordingly, it was advised that FLCs and all the rural branches of scheduled commercial banks should scale up financial literacy efforts through conduct of outdoor Financial Literacy Camps at least once a month, to facilitate financial inclusion through provision of two essentials i.e. “Financial Literacy” and easy „Financial Access“. Accordingly, 718 FLCs have been set up as at end of March 2013. A total of 2.2 million people have been educated through awareness camps, seminars and lectures during April 2012 to March 2013.

References

1. Malhotra R.N., “Banking in 1990’s, PIGMY”, Economic Review
2. Indian Finance & Investment guide.
3. Various Newspapers & International Journals
4. Seminar Rural Banking through ICT`
5. https://www.slideshare.net/sk_prince/rural-banking-in-india